

Pushing the Boundaries of Scalable 5G Core Networks: Cloud-Native NEF and CAPIF Interplay

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Abstract—The advent of Cloud-Native principles and architectures stands as a beacon of innovation in the design of the next generation of 5G/6G, promising a transition from initial (disaggregated) 5G Service-Based Architectures (SBA) implementations capable of running on the cloud to a truly distributed and scalable Cloud-Native 6G. However, the incumbent components and interfaces of the 5G core (5GC) pose barriers to the seamless integration of microservices. Challenges range from intricate Network Functions (NF) interdependencies to interface constraints and the absence of an event-driven architecture, which might jeopardise efficient microservice communication. This paper discusses the interplay between the Network Exposure Function (NEF) and the Common API Framework (CAPIF), defined by 3GPP, to standardize how network APIs are discovered, exposed, and consumed. First, we propose a novel microservice and event-driven Network Exposure Function (MNEF) built upon the NEF standard, featuring CAPIF support and various purpose-built microservices. Then, we evaluate its interoperability with reference implementations of 5GC (Open5GS) and CAPIF (OpenCAPIF) and its performance and scalability for handling large-scale request scenarios. The results attest to the MNEF’s benefits and interoperability with compliant 5GC implementations. Despite an additional (expected) overhead in communications, MNEF fulfils its purpose as defined in the 5G architecture, acting as an interface between external parties and 5G core NFs. Moreover, the proposed MNEF presents itself as a design solution that pushes the scalable 5G communication boundaries.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today’s 5G realm, cloud-native architectures are driving a paradigm shift. Cloud-nativeness offers innovative approaches for building efficient 5G networks. In light of that, this paper investigates the realization of one of the critical components in 5G Core — the Network Exposure Function (NEF) and its integration with Common API Framework (CAPIF). NEF was specified as a mediation entity to facilitate secure and efficient interaction between internal and external network functions [1]. On the other hand, CAPIF [2] provides a standardized abstraction for 5G network functions and services. Despite their specification, their intricate interdependencies, limited interface definitions, and the absence of a reference architecture present challenges in achieving the ultimate goal of a flexible, scalable, and consistent entry point for 5G/B5G core functions. Thus, this study contributes with a novel Microservice and Event-Driven Network Exposure Function (MNEF) architecture featuring native CAPIF support. In such

contribution, we debate its design, component’s role, and the 5GC and CAPIF integration. The MNEF offers dual benefits: it enhances the segmentation and scalability of network exposure, particularly relevant in large-scale scenarios; and provides consistent admission control to network functions by ensuring compatibility with CAPIF. The novelty of this proposal lies in its approach to addressing the challenges of Network Function (NF) integration and scalability within a Cloud-Native 5G. To the best of our knowledge, this work represents the first comprehensive study of NEF and CAPIF interplay within the context of a flexible and scalable 5G core architecture. We thoroughly evaluated the feasibility of the MNEF proposal by integrating it with Open5GS and OpenCAPIF, two widely used 5G Core and CAPIF open-source implementations.

The subsequent sections of this paper are structured as follows: Section II analyses the related work. Section III details the proposed MNEF. Section IV outlines the evaluation methodology. Section V presents the results and discussion. Finally, Section VI draws the concluding remarks.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The related work presented in this section is organized into three main subjects: Cloud-Native Architectures in 5G Networks; capabilities and applications of CAPIF; and existing NEF implementations. The authors in [3] addressed the first subject of Cloud-Nativeness by discussing the Service Based Architecture (SBA) of a 5G network for enabling flexibility. The work discussed the need for a microservice approach in the core’s NFs. In [4], the authors explore both the microservice approach and the cloud-nativeness concept. The work envisions a NEF based in microservices and a stateless gateway to connect requests to the correct NF. Concerning CAPIF related research, in [5], the standard for 3GPP Northbound APIs is explained. The authors showed how the CAPIF allows vertical applications and platforms to interact with a 3GPP-compliant 5G network. Some applications examples are European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC); EdgeApps; and Cellular Vehicle to Everything (C-V2X). The NEF represents a crucial role in this interaction as it is the bridge between the CAPIF and the Core Network (CN). In previous studies, some development

was made on CAPIF implementations, such as [6]. This work concluded that CAPIF is a crucial framework for Application Programming Interface (API) service provisioning in 3GPP systems across various vertical industries. This paper was the first to demonstrate this potential by implementing a CAPIF Core Function (CCF) compliant. The CCF implementation was designed to facilitate interactions among network components and vertical applications through API services. The implementation follows Cloud Natives principles, providing automated evaluation and comprehensive instructions for deploying their services. Another notable effort in integrating NEF and CAPIF was undertaken in the EVOLVED5G European project to connect vertical applications (Network Application) with NFs [7].

Lastly, in regards to NEF implementations, there is currently an open-source NEF simulator called NEFSim [8] that allows the testing of the northbound API in a simulated environment. Still, NEFSim does not allow interacting with a CN or southbound, or refer to CAPIF. Nokia’s commercial NEF solution [9] is described as a microservice-based architecture mainly relying on HTTP protocol. Despite that, its CAPIF integration is not detailed. In [10], a dynamic selection of 5G QoS Identifier (5QI) is proposed to deliver stable video quality. The authors mention the usage of a private 5G network and NEF, as well as the API call `Nnef_AFSessionWithQoS` that solicits Quality of Service (QoS) configurations in the CN and a higher priority 5QI. Although it is a similar approach to our study, no explanation of which core, Radio Access Network (RAN) or NEF used was given.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

The proposed architecture, depicted in Figure 1, comprises six key components: a Northbound Gateway (NGW) for handling Northbound RESTful requests from Application Functions (AFs) and converting them into event-oriented requests. An MQTT message broker persists and serves the event messages (i.e., the converted AF requests) in a publish-subscribe pattern. Four NEF microservices, each one implementing a specific NEF functionality – as a Proof of Concept (PoC), and based on NEF specification were implemented. In specific, it supports Event Monitoring, Traffic Influence, Analytics Exposure, and QoS Control based on their representativeness, concerning the NEF interaction with AFs, CAPIF, and 5G core. All persisting intermediary request states are persisted in a database. It contains a Southbound Gateway (SGW) for CAPIF and 5GC HTTP interfacing, and a reverse proxy is deployed to act as an arbitrator for external requests (both on AFs and 5GC sides), adding caching, load balancing, and security enforcement.

The proposed architecture underpinning the Cloud-Native paradigm was devised to enhance the processing capabilities of the NEF by logically separating them across smaller independent entities. The NEF functionalities were decomposed into loosely coupled microservices following a Domain-Driven and API-first design and adhering to the Single Responsibility Principle (SRP) for enhanced performance and scalability (i.e., stateless components capable of asynchronously handling and

Fig. 1. Proposed MNEF’s Architecture

scaling in response to fluctuations in AF request demand), and flexibility – allowing the system to be more resilient and focused on NEF API contracts rather than each functionality implementation. Indeed, NEF is required to handle heterogeneous types of AF requests. Some of them involve a multi-step interaction with the 5G core. The proposed design goes in line with the original idea of a Service Oriented 5G architecture, further extending the concept to align with a Cloud-Native approach that favours compartmentalization (and containerization) of individual functionalities and asynchronous communications (as opposed, for instance, to pure synchronous HTTP-based communications).

Such design is set to optimize the 5G network exposure and the interaction AFs and the 5G Core. Furthermore, by design, external AFs do not need to interact with the 5G core directly. AF request payloads and 5G core resource details are cached into the intermediate database, which makes the original request-reply scheme more isolated and efficient. CAPIF support was also incorporated at the NEF microservice level to further contribute to the idea of an interoperable (and expandable) NEF.

IV. METHODOLOGY

We devised a methodology for validating two main strands: the MNEF’s functional aspects, including its interoperability with OpenCAPIF and Open5GS, and the performance of the developed NEF PoC. For the first, we considered two reference scenarios described in the NEF and OpenCAPIF specifications: CAPIF’s service registration (cf. Fig. 2) using OpenCAPIF implementation¹ and NEF QoS control (cf. Fig. 3.) in tandem with Open5GS Core².

Two scenarios were strategically selected to maximize the NEF, CAPIF, and 5GC interoperability assessment. In the service registration case, AF, CAPIF and NEF must inter-operate and agree on a set of API contracts. Whereas in the QoS scenario, NEF must communicate with other 5GC constituents – the Policy Charging Function (PCF) in this case. We deployed the proposed MNEF and Open5GS in a single node Kubernetes cluster (Fig. 4), exposing the NEF Northbound and Southbound APIs through a LoadBalancer. The machine used for experiments has a 4-core CPU and

¹<https://ocf.etsi.org/>

²<https://open5gs.org/>

Fig. 2. AF-CAPIF-NEF Sequence diagram. [2]

Fig. 3. NEF QoS Control API Sequence diagram. [11]

16GB of RAM. The OpenCAPIF instance was deployed off-site and available via HTTPS.

Fig. 4. Validation Scenario, with NEF, OpenCAPIF and Open5GS

A. Performance KPIs

Table I summarizes the key NEF KPIs used for assessing the NEF's performance. We divided each KPI into three thresholds: Upgradable (U), Acceptable (A), and Optimal (O) based on related work and empirical knowledge from the authors.

TABLE I
KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)

#	Name	Target KPIs	Brief Description
1	Latency	$U \geq 50ms \geq A$ $\geq 20ms > O$	Latency introduced by the NEF when handling API requests and responses.
2	Throughput	$U \geq 40/s \geq A \geq 80/s > O$	Capacity to handle a high volume of API requests and responses per unit of time.
3	Resource Usage	$U \geq 90\% \geq A \geq 70\% > O$	Usage of resources. Mainly CPU, memory and network.
4	Response Time	$U \geq 70ms \geq A$ $\geq 30ms > O$	Time it takes for the NEF to respond to API requests.

The performance of MNEF was conducted by recreating high-load test scenarios. These tests aimed to understand the MNEF's ability to maintain functionality under high load. We segmented the tests into four scenarios, differing in replicas of the MNEF components. Scenario 1 - Baseline: One instance of each component. Scenario 2 - Multiple GW: Two instances NGW and SGW in a total of four. Scenario 3 - Two instances of each NEF API service. Scenario 4 - Scenario 2 and 3 combined. Then, we performed a three-stage testing set of 1/10/25 parallel processes for each scenario for 5 minutes. Each process generated a (QoS Control) request per second to the MNEF. Each MNEF microservice measured the round-trip time of requests to identify system bottlenecks and compare them with 5G Core request times. Resource usage (CPU% and RAM) was also monitored to assess potential throttling effects due to high request loads.

B. NEF and 5G Core Integration

The Open5GS integration tests consisted of sending requests, through an AF, to the endpoints of the NEF's `Nnef_AfSessionWithQoS` and `Nnef_TrafficInfluence` API services with various payloads and observe the effects on the Protocol Data Unit (PDU) session. The NEF translates the request and builds a new payload in a new format to be issued to the PCF `Npcf_PolicyAuthorization` Service API. During this, the NEF adds the appropriate parameters (media components, QoS configurations, etc) to the PCF payload to ensure that the flows are created or updated accordingly. Once the request reaches the PCF, the User Equipment (UE)'s PDU session changes are reflected, leveraging additional core NFs interaction, such as the Session Management Function (SMF) and User Plane Function (UPF). Examples of results produced include the creation or update of QoS flows, the addition of new Service Data Flow (SDF) filters (Fig. 5), or the removal of these QoS policies and filtering mechanisms. For these tests, a UE was configured in the core with unlimited Guaranteed Bit Rate (GBR), and then a request was issued to the `Nnef_AfSessionWithQoS` API changing the QoS parameters, such as maximum bitrate in Downlink and Uplink. This integration was validated with two approaches: checking log messages across the core's network functions, and traffic generation at the UEs to check

Fig. 8. CPU Usage on MNEF host

increased latency and response times, the NEF demonstrated the capability to handle higher loads than those attempted. The tests demonstrated that the MNEF is scalable and can efficiently manage increased traffic volumes while maintaining performance stability. TABLE II summarizes the best results across different tests.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE AND SCALABILITY RESULTS.

#	Name	1 Req/s	10 Req/s	25 Req/s
1	Latency	~28.5ms (Multiple GW)	~38.6ms (Multiple GW)	~70.7ms (Multiple GW)
2	Throughput	0.926/s (Multiple GW)	8.94/s (Multiple GW)	13.65/s (Combined)
3	Resource Usage	CPU: 4.61% RAM: 25.30% (Multiple MS)	CPU: 48.22% RAM: 26.55% (Multiple GW)	CPU: 49.56% RAM: 23.68% (Multiple MS)
4	Response Time	~79.6ms (Multiple GW)	~106ms (Multiple MS)	~344ms (Multiple MS)

The testing revealed some key areas of improvement. One notable issue was the bottleneck on the 5GC side, where the PCF service became overloaded, resulting in unreliable data in some cases. At maximum PCF load, response times did not meet expected targets, suggesting the need for improvements in code, design or hardware optimizations. Resource usage was generally consistent across environments. Still, the machine struggled with 25 requests per second due to delays from PCF restarts, leading to a marked increase in request delta times compared to earlier stages and CPU usage peak. Transitioning to a uniform and fully Cloud-Native platform is expected to further enhance the overall 5GC’s scalability by preventing bottlenecks in interdependent services – as encountered in this study – and contribute to a more efficient design. As we move towards 6G, the benefits of a Cloud-Native approach will be even more pronounced, addressing emerging complexities and enabling unprecedented levels of network flexibility and performance.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, we introduced a novel MNEF architecture leveraging Cloud-Native principles and CAPIF support to improve scalability, flexibility, and efficiency in 5GC. Key

findings revealed that the proposed MNEF integrated seamlessly with Open5GS and OpenCAPIF, efficiently managing high request loads through decentralized processes. Regardless of how the NEF architecture may evolve for 6G, the scalability and efficiency discussed will be critical for B5G/6G networks, which are anticipated to be fully distributed. Asynchronous communications and disaggregated services allow for better concurrent processing, scalability, and fault tolerance. Despite some high request loads straining the system, the MNEF could handle significant loads. By exposing NEF APIs through CAPIF, secure interactions are ensured, sensitive data is protected, and the integrity of communications is maintained. This is crucial for safeguarding the interconnected 5G infrastructure. The performance of 5G core functionalities (like the NEF/PCF integration) and their optimization through efficient and scalable designs are critical to achieving Beyond 5G/6G expectations. Future work should further explore the Cloud-Native paradigm and different hardware configurations to fully understand how the MNEF’s design can be extended to a broader range of services and the scalability and robustness of 5G/6G networks.

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